

Supplementary Table 1 – Patient Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for Human studies

	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria	Ref.
Human	Patients undergoing AAA repair operations. Control samples from non-aneurysmal aortic samples collected at autopsy.	Not explicitly specified.	(1)
	Patients undergoing AAA repair operations. Control samples from age-matched patients without cardiovascular disease (autopsy) and volunteers (serum samples).	Not explicitly specified.	(2)
	Patients with AAA without peripheral arterial occlusive disease (PAD). Patients with PA and healthy volunteers without PAD or AAA as controls.	Recent tumor/chemotherapy (<1 year), autoimmune/hematological diseases, unstable angina, organ transplantation, and PAD in subgroup analysis.	(3)
	Patients with asymptomatic infrarenal AAA (≥ 3 cm). Control patients without AAA (aortic diameter <3 cm).	AAA >5.5 cm (males), >5 cm (females), ruptured or symptomatic AAA, prior AAA repair, mycotic/inflammatory AAA, sepsis (<3 months), malignancy, thoracic aneurysms, or dissections.	(4)
	Patients undergoing TAA repair surgery. Control patients undergoing surgery for coronary artery bypass grafting or aortic valve replacement surgery.	Genetic diseases (e.g., Marfan syndrome), aortitis, malignancy.	(5)
	Patients with atherosclerotic TAA and AAA vs. healthy controls for the discovery study. Patients with TAA, AAA, AD vs. patients with inherited arrhythmia without history of AA, atherosclerotic disease, hyperlipidaemia, hypertension, or diabetes as control subjects for the validation study.	Hereditary connective tissue diseases, renal insufficiency, familial hypercholesterolemia, prior aortic surgery, and multiple aneurysms or dissections.	(6)

Supplementary Table 2 – Patient Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for Human and Experimental studies

	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria	Ref.
Human and experimental	Patients undergoing elective AAA repair operations.	Not explicitly specified.	(7)
	Patients undergoing elective AAA repair operations. Sera obtained from consented individuals.	Not explicitly specified.	(8)
	Patients undergoing repair surgery for thoracic aortic dissection. Control aortas obtained from heart transplantation donors. Blood samples from patients with thoracic aortic aneurysm and dissection collected before intervention and non- thoracic aortic aneurysm and dissection controls.	Not explicitly specified.	(9)
	Patients undergoing aortic dissection repair surgery before rupture. Control aortas obtained from heart transplantation donors. Blood samples from newly diagnosed patients with thoracic aortic dissection prior to rupture and treatment intervention and control samples from age-matched non-thoracic aortic dissection individuals undergoing regular physical examinations.	Patients with known genetic syndromes related to aortic disease (e.g., Marfan, Turner, Loeys–Dietz, or Ehlers–Danlos syndrome).	(10)

Supplementary Literature

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